

Effect of temperature and mating on reproductive biology of rice armyworm adults fed with 10% sucrose solution.^a Hisar, India.

Temperature (°C)	Age of adults before release		Association period	Preoviposition period (d)	Oviposition period (d)	Postoviposition period (d)	Adult longevity (d)		Eggs (no./female)	Hatching (%)
	Male	Female					Male	Female		
15±1.5	Fresh	Fresh	To death	7	19	2	29	28	939	70
15±1.5	Fresh	–	None	–	–	–	30	–	–	–
15±1.5	–	Fresh	None	–	–	–	–	29	–	–
18±1.5	Fresh	12 d	5 d	12	11	2	29	25	370	45
20±1.5	Fresh	Fresh	2 d	13	3	1	16	17	192	0
20±1.5	Fresh	Fresh	3 d	13	1	3	11	17	53	0
20±1.5	Fresh	Fresh	To death	8	10	2	21	20	606	42
25±1.8	Fresh	Fresh	To death	9	5	1	16	15	457	68
25±1.8	Fresh	6 d	6 d	11	3	2	13	16	406	65
25±1.8	6 d	Fresh	To death	10	4	3	12	17	380	45
30±2.2	Fresh	Fresh	To death	6	8	3	17	17	743	25
30±2.2	6 d	Fresh	To death	7	7	1	17	15	600	32
30±2.2	Fresh	6 d	To death	11	6	1	12	18	523	30
30±2.2	9 d	Fresh	To death	10	9	1	18	20	600	40

^aAv of 10 replications, 1 pair (female + male) of adults/replication.

individually in separate glass jars (15 × 10 cm) containing dry sugarcane leaves for egg laying.

In the first set, adults were kept without food or water; in the second, with water alone; in the third, with 10% sucrose solution. Adults remained together for different periods.

Adults without food did not survive more than 6 d at all temperatures and

died without laying eggs. Water-satiated adults also did not lay eggs and survived 4-8 d. Sucrose-fed females laid eggs at all temperatures (see table).

Mating was essential for oviposition; unmated females did not lay eggs even when males were in the same glass jar but kept away by wire gauge. When the adults were brought together, mating

took place within 48 h to 12 d after emergence. Continuous association of adults resulted in higher egg output; 2-3 d association resulted in unfertilized and fewer eggs. Adult longevity, egg output, hatching, and oviposition period were maximum at 15 °C. At 30 °C, adult longevity and hatching were considerably reduced. □

Effect of transplanting date on leafhopper (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and rice bug (RB) *Leptocorisa oratorius* infestation at Kuningan, West Java

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An experiment in Kuningan (550 m above sea level) in the 1985 wet season evaluated the effect of transplanting date and insecticide application on rice pest infestation. Variety Cisanggarung was transplanted in a split-plot arrangement with transplanting date as main plots and insecticide application as subplots with three replications. The subplots were 5 × 5 m. LF infestation was assessed by counting the number of tillers with insects on 20 hills.

LF infestation with late transplanting (1 mo after farmers' date) was lower than with early (1 mo before farmers' date) or simultaneous transplanting

Table 1. Effect of transplanting date on LF and RB infestation, and yield of rice variety Cisanggarung.^a SURIF, West Java, Indonesia, 1985 wet season.

Transplanting date	Infestation ^b				Yield (g/20 hills)
	Tillers with LF (no./20 hills)			RB (no./25 m ²)	
	22 DT	42 DT	63 DT		
Early (30 Dec 1985)	3.45 b	10.83 b	15.10 b	26.89 b	479 a
Simultaneous (30 Jan 1986)	3.47 b	10.82 b	4.06 a	9.56 a	509 a
Late (2 Mar 1986)	2.07 a	4.06 a	4.06 a	302.00 c	314 b
CV (%)	28.8	9.0	5.8	18.9	14.0

^a In a column, numbers followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by HSD. ^b DT = days after transplanting.

Table 2. Effect of diazinon and BPMC on LF infestation.^a SURIF, 1985 wet season.

Treatment	Tillers with LF ^a (no./20 hills)		
	22 DT	42 DT	63 DT
Control	3.47 b	8.10 b	1.13 a
Diazinon	2.66 a	1.64 a	1.44 a
BPMC	2.80 ab	9.36 b	8.05 a
CV (%)	18.4	7.1	7.4

^a In a column, numbers followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by HSD.

(Table 1). In contrast, RB infestation was highest with late transplanting. The yield with late transplanting was significantly lower than with early or simultaneous transplanting, presumably because of heavy RB infestation.

Diazinon was more effective than BPMC in LF control (Table 2). Insecticides had no effect on RB infestation because they were applied at the very early flowering stage, and had no residual effect when infestation occurred. □